

TIME MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF LANGUAGE STUDENT OF COLLEGE OF TEACHER EDUCATION

BABY S. ABAGON

Associate Professor, President Ramon Magsaysay State University, Iba Campus, Iba, Zambales, Philippines.
Corresponding Email Address: abagonbaby28@gmail.com

Abstract

Time management is a practice of organizing, planning and preparing on how to divide the time between different activities and academic performances. Using the quantitative method of research design to achieve the breadth of understanding of the study, the investigation involved forty-four (44) language student- respondents in the College of Teacher Education, A.Y. 2022-2023. To gather the relevant data, the survey questionnaires were determined to a four –point rating scale. Time attitude was the highly practice compare to the time planning and time wasting. While time planning; time attitude; and time wasting has a significant difference when group according to the language students profile. On this account, the need to address this finding is truly evident. Hence, the results of this study will be utilized as basis for the authorities of the College of Teacher Education may develop successful time management strategies to develop good time management habits of the students.

Keywords: Language Students, Time Management, Time Planning, Time Wasting, Academic performance

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important ways for the students to save time is an effective time planning. Student should make usage of time efficiently by making advance planning; should determine study time and shouldn't postpone; and should not leave the discipline in this respect. For students, time management is very important to be able to achieve success in the academic sense. By planning, organizing and take time correctly, the expectation for attain the desired success will increase. Qualified use of time should be properly used (Türe 2013).

There is a great emphasis on the effective and efficient time management practices considered as the key to success in life (Pugh & Nathwani, 2017; Nasrullah & Khan, 2015). It is a must and important to know what problems will you be faced and to know the reasons of the problems or challenges in order to apply time management effectively and efficiently. Time management is recognized as an important component of work performance and professional practice just like teachers, teachers using different strategies of time management. Learning time management skills in teachers lets work smarter instead of harder. According to Savino (2016), time management is a form of self-management with a clear focus on time in understanding what activities to do; how to do them more efficiently and effectively; in what time it should be done and when is the correct time to the particular task.

Meanwhile, the time management behavior has three basic surfaces the time attitudes, long-range planning and short-range planning (Aeon & Aguinis, 2017). Time is significant, especially to students, there are school works and house chores needed to be finished, and student should not waste time in his or her life. It is very important that a student has what called "time management." Time management is an important skill that greatly aided learners'

academic performances. It helps you to organize and plan how to divide time between specific activities. While, time attitude is the positive or negative perspective towards academic achievement and good performance (Nieuwoudt, & Brickhill, 2017). The concept of handling everyday task by the students and teacher for longer period of time, the competence in long range planning. Planning in the short run for the day to day activity is short-range planning. Factors include students' attitudes and behavior affects the time management (Karim, et. al, 2015). Time management is a highly discussed topic nowadays especially in the new normal and time wasters is a part of time management. Time waster inhibits us from achieving goals in the most effective and efficient way.

Time wasting activities (time wasters) are part of time management. The time management is a way how to work more productive and more effective. This issue may help us to avoid time-consuming activities, interruption or distractions. We can prioritize tasks, set limits, plan daily problems and tasks, and learn how to manage unpredictable tasks. If we identify our goals, we will know which task is important. Time management helps us to allocate time resources (Varga, 2011).

2. OBJECTIVE

This study aimed to determine the time management practices of language students' academic performance of the College of Teacher Education.

Specifically, it targeted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the Demographic profile of the student respondents in term of
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 Parents Occupation; and
 - 1.4 Time schedule using gadget?
2. What is the Level of Time Management practices of language student respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 Time planning;
 - 2.2 Time attitude; and
 - 2.3 Time Wasting?
3. Is there a significant difference between time management practices when grouped according to their profile?
4. What propose action plan and strategies to be developed to enhance the time management practices?

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

a. Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design. This method placed primary emphasis on generalizability. It quantified the responses of the respondents on the survey questionnaire.

b. Respondents and Location

The researcher targeted only the language students which consist of forty-four (44) language student- respondents in the College of Teacher Education, A.Y. 2022-2023.

c. Sampling Technique

The researcher use a simple random sampling technique to examine the entire population of language student in the College of Teacher Education at President Ramon Magsaysay State University and give an equal chance of being chosen as respondents. As stated by Hayes (2023) simple random sample is a subset of a statistical population in which each member of the subset has an equal probability of being chosen. He also stated that a simple random sample is meant to be an unbiased representation of a group.

d. Research Instrumentation

The researchers adapt the main instrument of Razali, Rusiman, Gan, and Arbin (2017) with the title of study "The Impact of Time Management on Students' Academic Achievement". But there are some modifications that was made to adapt the instrument to the Philippine educational setting. The first part of the questionnaire contains the demographic profile of the student-respondent in terms of age, sex, parents occupation and time schedule using gadget, academic performance for the 1st semester and the level of time management practices of the language student-respondent in terms of time planning, time attitude, and time wasting.

e. Data Gathering Procedure

This study follow three phases of gathering data, which include validation of the research questionnaire, permission and approval of the research questionnaire, and administration and retrieval of the questionnaire.

Phase 1. Validation of the research instrument. To reduce the likelihood of misinterpretation, a group of subject matter experts review and validate the modified research questionnaire's indicators/items (Razali et al. 2017).

Phase 2. Permission and approval of the research instrument. A formal letter sent to the office of the Dean of the College of Teacher Education. Then, a letter of permission with the approval of the dean is sent to the language Teacher to seek help to administer the research questionnaire using the Google form.

Phase 3. Administration and retrieval of questionnaire. Research questionnaires was sent to the language students. Considering the learning modality of schools, the distribution and retrieval of research questionnaires was done using an online approach.

f. Statistical Treatment of Data

Data that is collected from the questionnaire will be tallied, analyzed, and summarized accordingly.

1. **Weighted Mean** – This was used in order to determine the overall perception of the respondents on the time management practices under the new normal.
2. **Frequency** – This was used to presents data in the form of a table using class intervals and frequencies.
3. **ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)** – This was used to analyze the difference between the means of more than two groups.
4. **Likert Scale** – This was used to scale responses in survey research to measure level of practices of the respondents.

Likert Scale in the Evaluation of Time Management Personal Assessment Practice

Range	Scale	Interpretation	Symbol
3.26- 4.0	4	Always Practice	AP
2.51- 3.25	3	Often Practice	OP
1.76 -2.5	2	Rarely Practice	RP
1.0 - 1.75	1	Never Practice	NP

f. Ethical Consideration

To establish sound and ethical research, the researcher considered various ethical procedures in acquiring, analyzing, and accomplishing the data to be gathered.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Profile of the Respondents

4.1.1 Age

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Profile of Respondents' In terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 – 22	42	95.5
23 – 27	1	2.3
28 – 32	1	2.3
Total	44	100.0
Mean Age:20.3 or 20 Years old		

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage distribution according to age. Forty two (42) or 95.5% whose age is between 18-22; one (1) or 2.3% whose age is between 23-27 and one (1) or 2.3% who's age is between 28-32. The mean age is 20.3 or 20 years old. This result implied that the age of the respondents belongs to young adulthood.

According to the National Academic Press (2015) young adulthood developed critical period in the life course.

4.1.2 Sex

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Profile of Respondents' In terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	11	25.0
Female	33	75.0
Total	44	100.0

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to sex. Eleven (11) or 25% whose she's is male and thirty-three (33) or 75% whose sex is female. The result implied the dominance of the female respondents. Female students possessed more effective time management skills than male students.

A comparative study of male and female students in relation to time management skills was hypothesized that female students tend to be high on time management skills than male students. (Rani, Usha; Sharma, 2018).

4.1.3 Occupation

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Profile of Respondents' In terms of Parents Occupation

Parents Occupation	Frequency	Percent
Government Employee	9	20.5
Farmer	6	13.6
Fisherman	1	2.3
Businessman/Woman	4	9.1
Vendor	24	54.5
Total	44	100.0

Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to parent's occupation. This shows that there are nine (9) or 20.5 % whose occupation is government employee; six (6) or 13.6% whose occupation is farmer; one on 2.3 % whose occupation is fisherman; or 9.1% whose occupation is businessman/woman and twenty our (24) or 54.5% whose occupation is vendor. The table shows the dominance of the vendor as parent's occupation of the respondents.

As stated to the study of Bhowmik (2013) 25 percent of vendors are illiterate, while 22 percent have only received a primary education. The remaining 32% have higher education credentials, whereas just 32% have completed secondary schooling. Some of them were graduates who chose the industry since there were no other employment opportunities.

4.1.4 Time Schedule Using Gadget

Table 4: Frequency and Percentage Distribution on the Profile of Respondents' In terms of Time Schedule using gadget

Time Schedule using gadget	Frequency	Percent
1-2	2	4.5
2-3	4	9.1
4-5	8	18.2
6-7	11	25.0
8--9	19	43.2
Total	44	100.0
Average Time: 6.4 or 6 hrs.		

Table 4 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to the time schedule using gadget. This shows that there are nineteen (19) or 43.2% who's 8-9 hours or using gadget; eleven (11) or 25% having 6-7 hours; eight (8) or 18.2 % were using 4-5 hours; four (4) or 9.1% were using 2-3 hours and two (2) or 4.5% having 1-2 hours of time using gadget. In this table it tell us that the average time they use using gadget is 6.4 or 6 hours. The results showed that the average time they use using gadget is 6.4 or 6 hours.

They spending time more than 6 hours on gadget because on the assignment and leisure. Similar results emerged from a study in Malaysia by Othman (2020), which showed that students were spending time more than 6 hours on gadget.

4.2 Level of Time Management

4.2.1 Time Planning

Table 5: Mean Rating in the Level of Time Management Practices of Student respondent in terms of Time Planning

	Time Planning	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Rank
1	I make a list of activities that should be done for a week.	3.27	Always Practice	4
2	I have set a goal for each week.	3.09	Often Practice	9
3	I do things in order of my priorities.	3.39	Always Practice	2
4	I set my time in completing a task.	3.18	Often Practice	8
5	I prioritize the task based on when the assignment is due and how much time I need to complete it.	3.61	Always Practice	1
6	I divided the easy and difficult task	3.30	Always Practice	3
7	I always write down academic dates so that I can get it done on time.	3.27	Always Practice	4
8	I make time for activities and for family	3.27	Always Practice	4
9	I make reminders in sticky notes	3.00	Often Practice	10
10	I divide my time for doing activities and making rest.	3.27	Always Practice	4
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.22	Always Practice	

Table 5 shows the mean rating in the level of time management practices of language student respondent in terms of time planning.

Indicator number five (5), “I prioritize the task based on when the assignment is due and how much time I need to complete it.” has weighted mean of 3.61%, described as always practice and ranked 1st. It implies that students prioritize their given tasks because they have a deadline and they need to submit them before the due date that was set in Edmodo, unlike household chores that have no deadline to finish or to complete. According to Cyril (2015) people need to prioritize their lists and tasks and consider assignment due as one of the factors that can affect the final grade or academic performance of the students.

Indicator number nine (9), “I make reminders in sticky notes.” has weighted mean of 3.00%, describe as often practice and ranked at 10th. It implies that students often used sticky notes because Edmodo will always make reminders about the deadline of their tasks. Wells (2015) noted that there’s no longer a need to stick reminder notes all over your desk! Students can personalize their notification settings to get updates on any upcoming events, class assignments and quizzes, and messages from Teachers.

In this table it tells us that 3.22 is the overall weighted mean which implies that respondents are always practice their level of Time Management in terms of Time planning. In general the students response are always practice which means that they were still able to manage their time in terms of time planning. They moderately manage their time in doing things in order of priority, planning what needs to be done during the day and dividing their time in doing activities. This gives an implication that having a set schedule everyday does not affect much on the students-respondents level of time management practices. Students can complete their work on time, stay involved in their studies and have more time free to pursue things that are important to them, such as sports, hobbies and spending time with friends and families, by having time planning.

Time planning is an important to both college students and educators. Educators are worried that students will spend sufficient time, especially study time on academics, while students are concerned numerous demands on their time. As Macan (2012). In trying to read all the books, chapters and readings assigned, meet paper task deadlines, and participate in extracurricular activities in the school, college students become overwhelmed with feelings that there is not enough time to complete all their work adequately and correctly. Given this time pressure, successful time planning is considered important by college students.

4.2.2 Time Attitude

Table 6: Mean Rating in the Level of Time Management Practices of Student respondent in terms of Time Attitude

Time Attitude	Mean	Descriptive Rating	Rank
I proofread my activities before submitting.	3.39	Always Practice	3
I do my activities advanced, week before the deadline.	2.89	Often Practice	9
I study my difficult task without procrastinating.	2.64	Often Practice	10
Priorities are something I set and stick to.	3.09	Often Practice	5
I can make quick decisions on trivial matters.	2.91	Often Practice	8
I feel I use my schedule correctly and effectively.	2.95	Often Practice	6
I regularly review my activities in relation to my goals.	2.93	Often Practice	7

I assure that all my activities will be submitted on or before the deadline.	3.66	Always Practice	1
I am using other references to have relation in my answers	3.18	Often Practice	4
I always add information that strengthen my answers.	3.41	Always Practice	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.23	Always Practice	

Table 6 shows the mean rating in the level of time management practices of language student respondent in terms of time attitude.

Indicator number eight (8), “I assure that all my activities will be submitted on or before the deadline.” has weighted mean of 3.66%, describe as always practice and ranked at 1st. It implies that the students guaranteed that they will submit all of their activities on or before the deadline. Students submit all of their tasks to have a good grade and finalizing to avoid forgetting about it. As Gregory and Garcia cited (2015) it is evident that a student will submit work very early with motives to do the task appear simple.

Indicator number three (3), “I study my difficult task without procrastinating.” has weighted mean of 2.64%, describe as often practice ranked at number 10th. It implies that students work diligently on their challenging task. According to Hebing (2016) that procrastination would be higher when task difficulty was higher.

The overall weighted mean is 3.23% and described as always practice. In general, the result is always practice which means that the students know how to prioritize their activities. Students who know how to prioritize things are more productive and make better use of their time. It helps the students in determining which tasks are the most critical and urgent, as well as how much time they should devote to each. According to the research, time management practices are linked to an individual's awareness and attitudes regarding time management, as well as their belief of having control over time. As a result, time attitudes include the impression that an individual is in command of his or her time, the perception that an individual is effectively managing his or her time, and the perception that an individual is making productive use of time (Karim et al., 2015)

4.2.3 Time Wasting

Table 7: Mean Rating in the Level of Time Management Practices of Student respondent in terms of Time Wasting

Time Wasting		Descriptive Rating	Rank
I do my activities rushing at last minute.	2.41	Rarely Practice	7
I find myself making leisure with other media platforms that interfere with my activities/school works.	2.77	Often Practice	4
I prioritize sleeping than doing activities/school works in advanced because deadline is too far	2.45	Rarely Practices	6
I am satisfied come what may as long as I finished my activities.	3.07	Often Practice	2
I am making empty promises to do my activities, but in the end will not do it.	2.30	Rarely Practice	9
I am spending precious minutes dealing with things that are not my priority and distracts me from doing school related stuff.	2.30	Rarely Practice	9
I discipline myself in using my cellphone.	2.84	Often Practice	3

I delay my activities because of poor internet connection.	2.52	Often Practice	5
My actions are mainly decided by me, not others.	3.32	Always Practice	1
I always procrastinate	2.36	Rarely Practice	8
Overall Weighted Mean	2.67	Often Practice	

Table 7 shows the mean rating in the level of time management practices of language student respondent in terms of time wasting.

Indicator number nine (9), “My actions are mainly decided by me, not others.” Has weighted mean of 3.32%, describe as always practice, equivalent to rank 1. It implies that students actions are largely determined by them, rather than by others. Students have their own decisions about their actions because they are big enough to listen to other people. The results of the study indicate that student involvement and students who made the decision themselves felt motivated and had good academic performance in their end of term examinations (Chandi et al., 2016). Indicator number five (5), “I am making empty promises to do my activities, but in the end will not do It.” has weighted mean of 2.30%, describe as rarely practice, equivalent to rank 9. It implies that students make hollow promises to complete their activities, but do not follow through because of spending more time doing leisure activities. Procrastination can be defined as the intentional delay of a task (Nordbyl et al., 2017).

Indicator number six (6), “I am spending precious minutes dealing with things that are not my priority and distracts me from doing school related stuff.” has weighted mean of 2.30%, describe as rarely practice, equivalent to rank 9. It implies that student’s waste time dealing with things that are not important to them, diverting their attention away from schoolwork because they are distracted on moving their attention back and forth between studying and various forms of technology. Based on Howard (2015) study the student often switch from studying to doing something related to technology such as checking email, Facebook, texting or watching TV and other media, 80% of students reported switch between studying and technology somewhat often to very often.

The overall weighted mean is 2.67% and described as often practice. The overall analysis is often practice. Time wasting may result of unclear information. If we do not understand well our tasks, we do not even use our time well. We can spend a lot of time thinking about it and wondering what we have to do, instead of working. (Margol 2014). With the corroboration of the study of Varshney (2016) majority of students have no good command on time management practices. Insufficient time management skills that adversely influence their social and academic performance. The use of time by students in advanced education organizations were identified as their everyday schedules and exercises. And the last is most of the students end up wasting their time unproductively.

4.3 Significant Relationship between the Level of Time Management Practices of Student respondent and Academic Performance

Time Planning

The computed significant value of sex is 0.00, age is 0.00, parents' occupation is 0.00 and time schedule using gadget is 0.00, which all are lower than (<) significant difference of 0.05, the

null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is no significant difference between the level of time management practices of student in terms of time planning to the profile variables of sex, age, parents' occupation and time schedule using gadgets. The result implied that the age, sex, parents' occupation and time schedule using gadget affects the level of time management practices in terms of time planning. Specially in prioritizing the task based on when the assignment is due and how much time needed to accomplish.

Table 8: Analysis of Variance to tests differences on the Level of Time Management Practices of Student respondent in Time Planning when grouped according to their profile variables

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Sex	Between Groups	7.31	2	3.66	8.99	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	16.68	41	0.41			
	Total	24.00	43				
Age	Between Groups	7.90	1	7.90	20.62	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	16.10	42	0.38			
	Total	24.00	43				
Parents Occupation	Between Groups	16.90	4	4.23	23.22	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	7.10	39	0.18			
	Total	24.00	43				
Time Schedule Using Gadgets	Between Groups	17.59	4	4.40	26.77	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	6.41	39	0.16			
	Total	24.00	43				

Time planning can be very useful in a student's hectic schedule. It ensures that students are well prepared, organized and focused to manage their daily lives and complete academic assignments on time. It can lead to improved success. Good time planning skills stems from the issue of prioritizing one's time effectively, Alex, K. (2019).

Time Attitude

The computed significant value of sex is 0.00, age is 0.00, parents' occupation is 0.00 and time schedule using gadget is 0.00, which all are lower than (<) significant difference of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is no significant difference between the level of time management practices of student in terms of time attitude to the profile variables of sex, age, parents' occupation and time schedule using gadgets. The result implied that the age, sex, parents' occupation and time schedule using gadget affects the level of time management practices in terms of time attitude in assuring that all activities will be submitted on or before the deadline.

Table 9: Analysis of Variance to tests differences on the Level of Time Management Practices of Student respondent in Time Attitude when grouped according to their profile variables

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Sex	Between Groups	6.41	2	3.20	10.76	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	12.21	41	0.30			
	Total	18.62	43				
Age	Between Groups	7.47	1	7.47	28.14	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	11.15	42	0.27			
	Total	18.62	43				
Parents Occupation	Between Groups	11.17	4	2.79	14.63	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	7.45	39	0.19			
	Total	18.62	43				
Time Schedule Using Gadgets	Between Groups	13.14	4	3.29	23.41	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	5.47	39	0.14			
	Total	18.62	43				

Chenna (2014) cited that the students must change their habits in order to have good time management skills. This can only happen if students take the first steps in identifying their problems. Good time management skills from the issue of prioritizing one's time effectively. This can be done by setting new personal goals and striving to accomplish them with a new and improved attitude in mind.

Time Wasting

Table 10: Analysis of Variance to tests differences on the Level of Time Management Practices of Student respondent in Time Wasting when grouped according to their profile variables

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Interpretation
Sex	Between Groups	5.26	2	2.63	4.94	0.01	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	21.84	41	0.53			
	Total	27.10	43				
Age	Between Groups	13.94	1	13.94	44.51	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	13.16	42	0.31			
	Total	27.10	43				
Parents Occupation	Between Groups	21.37	4	5.34	36.40	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	5.73	39	0.15			
	Total	27.10	43				
Time Schedule Using Gadgets	Between Groups	22.21	4	5.55	44.34	0.00	Reject Ho Significant
	Within Groups	4.88	39	0.13			
	Total	27.10	43				

The computed significant value of sex is 0.01, age is 0.00, parents' occupation is 0.00 and time schedule using gadget is 0.00, which all are lower than (<) significant difference of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, therefore, there is no significant difference between the level of time management practices of student in terms of time wasting to the profile variables of sex, age,

parents' occupation and time schedule using gadgets. The result implied that the age, sex, parents' occupation and time schedule using gadget affects the level of time management practices in terms of time wasting in deciding actions.

Farah (2017) explained that time wasting is an impediment to doing the required work efficiently and thus not achieving the desired goals on their predetermined dates. The concept of waste of time is a dynamic concept that changes by time, space, and people. It is the use of time in an appropriate manner, an activity that takes time, or a work that does not generate a response commensurate with the time spent for it.

4.4 Action plan and strategies to be developed to enhance the time management practices

Action Plan and Implementation of Time Management Strategies

Key Area	Objective	Time Management Strategies	Activities	Person responsible	Expected Outcomes
Time planning	To be more productive with time and identify daily priorities.	1.Using Sticky notes 2. Set a goal 3.Set time in completing task	Lecture Seminar	Language learners Teachers	Set clear, achievable goals for work, eliminating wasted time on unclear or irrelevant tasks.
Time attitude	To perform better in daily tasks and responsibilities	1.Projects Plan 2.Advance activities 3. Quick decision	Lecture Seminar	Language learners Teachers	More manageable chunks less procrastinating task
Time Wasting	To avoid wasting time in unproductive actions, works and disciplines.	1.My actions, my decisions 2.My work, my satisfaction. 3.My cellphone, my discipline	Lecture Seminar	Language learners Teachers	Maintain a healthy work-life balance

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn: 1). The student-respondents were female, age of 20, their parents' occupation is vendor and they use gadget for 6 hours. 2). The Level of Time Management practices of student-respondents is always practice in prioritizing the task based on when the assignment is due and how much time need to complete it for the time planning, always practice in assuring that all the activities will be submitted on or before the deadline for the time attitude and rarely practice in their actions that are mainly decided by them and not others for the time wasting. 3). There is a significant difference between the level of time management practices in terms of Time Planning, Time Attitude and Time Wasting to the sex, age, parents' occupation and time schedule using gadget. 4. Due to the result of the time management practices, the researcher develop propose action plan and implementation of management strategies to enhance the time management practices of the language students.

The following recommendations are advanced by the researcher based on the findings and conclusions generated in the study: 1). Teachers should always remind students to jot down their schedules in online classes and activity deadlines using a traditional sticky note so they can catch up with their good performance. 2). Students should always reread their lessons so they can easily answer their difficult tasks. 3). Teachers should give students tasks that are not necessary to submit but serve as a means of reviewing their lessons. 4). Teachers should always remind their students to proof read their completed tasks during their free time. 5). The teacher may have developed successful time management strategies to develop good time management habits of the students. 6). Future researcher may conduct another study similar to the current research and include other variables for development of research.

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